

**THE EVALUATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION
IMPLEMENTATION FOR STUDENTS
WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY
IN VICTORY PLUS PRIMARY SCHOOL**

Citra Dianingtyas,

Asep Supena,

Totok Bintoroⁱ

Post-Graduate Program,

Jakarta State University,

Indonesia

Abstract:

This research aims to evaluate the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability in a primary school. There are eight sub-focus of this research: the profile of students with intellectual disability, the teacher's competencies, the curriculum being used, the facilities, the learning process, the evaluation being used, the parents, and the supporting and challenging factors. This research was carried out in Sekolah Dasar Victory Plus, located in Bekasi, West Java province, Indonesia, involving 3 students who have been diagnosed as intellectually disabled. One with IQ score of 65 (in grade 4), one with IQ score of 66 (in grade 1) and one with IQ score of 68 (in grade three). It is conducted using qualitative evaluation method to get detailed and thorough descriptions. The data used in this research are derived from interviews, observations, and documentations analysis. Research findings show that the school has been trying to provide effective inclusive education for students with intellectual disability. The effort is apparent from the presence of shadow teachers who are assigned by the school to guide the students with intellectual disability in the teaching and learning process. However, in general, it can be concluded that the implementation of inclusive education in this school has not been undertaken optimally, specifically related to curriculum modification, the presence of special education teacher, and also the facilities. It needs a strong commitment from the school, the government, and the society to fulfill the requirements in implementing an effective inclusive education.

Keywords: intellectual disability, inclusive education

ⁱ Correspondence: email citra.dianingtyas@gmail.com, supena2007@yahoo.com, t.bintoro.tb@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Education is the right of every citizen of the world without any exception. The right to get education is stated in article 26 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which was organized by United Nations on December 10th, 1948. It is written that every person has the right to be entitled to education. This matter has also becomes the main priority in every country in the world, and it is proven by the convention of World Education Forum in Dakar, Senegal in 2000. All the countries were committed to actualize Education for All to every citizen in every level of society. This also applies in Indonesia, where every citizen unexceptionally has the right to get a decent education. In article 5 paragraph 1 of Constitution Number 20, 2003, it is stated that, "Every citizen has the same right to receive a good quality of education". It indicates that education is meant for every citizen, including those with physical, emotional, mental and social disabilities.

In 1994, a world conference was held in Salamanca regarding to Special Needs Education. It generated a declaration which was known as Salamanca Declaration. An important point stated in the declaration is that every child has different characteristics, interests, capabilities and needs of learning. Therefore, the education system and program should be designed by considering those diversities. It is also stated that children with special needs have the right to an access to regular schools which can accommodate their learning needs. This declaration becomes one of the foundations for the development of inclusive education in the world.

In Indonesia, inclusive education is covered by Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009. In article 2, it is mentioned that inclusive education aims to provide a wide range of opportunity to all students with physical, emotional, mental and social disabilities, as well as students with potential intelligence and/or special gifts to get a good quality of education in accordance to their needs and capabilities. Furthermore, inclusive education aims to actualize the implementation of education which appreciates diversity and indiscriminative for every student.

The implementation of inclusive education is certainly not as easy as turning the palm of the hand. To accommodate and facilitate the students' learning with different characteristics, interests, capabilities and needs is obviously a challenge for all the parties involved. In reality, based on the research done by Sunardi (in Sunardi & Sunaryo, 2011), there are still some obstacles found in implementing inclusive education in Indonesia. One of which is that inclusive education for students with disabilities has not been understood as an effort to improve the quality of education yet. It is still viewed as an effort to incorporate students with disabilities to a regular school in order to give the right to education, easy access, and indiscriminative attitude.

Another problem in implementing inclusive education according to Sunardi (in Sunardi & Sunaryo, 2011) is that the current curriculum has not accommodated the presence of children with different capabilities yet. Since the teachers are still finding difficulties in modifying the curriculum and learning strategies, so the curriculum used for students with special needs is still the same one used by the other normal students.

How inclusive education is implemented at schools in real life becomes the main reason for this research. The criteria of the evaluation refers to Indonesian Government Regulation number 19, 2005 about National Education Standards, Regulation of the Minister of Education number 70, 2009 about inclusive education, and also theories and guidance about inclusive education. This research was conducted in Victory Plus Primary School, Bekasi City, West Java Province, Indonesia. The aim is to evaluate the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability, and to give recommendations and inputs which can be beneficial for its improvements and refinements.

Children with intellectual disability are those who experience a significant retardation in their intelligence function that makes them need a special education service to be able to develop the potentials within them (Supena, 2015). Kustawan (2012) stated that children with intellectual disability are those whose intelligence level are significantly below average, accompanied by the inability in behavioral adaptation which appears in their developmental periods. In *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders Fifth Edition (DSM-5)*, it is written that “*Intellectual Disability is a disorder with onset during the developmental period that includes both intellectual and adaptive functioning deficits in conceptual, social, and practical domains.*” It is stated furthermore that the most important feature in intellectual disability is the existence of a general mental deficiency and the lack of adaptive function in daily life compared to other children of his age, with the same gender, from the same social-cultural environment.

According to Supena (2009), operationally, there are three main criteria which are often used by the experts to classify a child as intellectually disabled. They are: (1) the intellectual ability is significantly below average, generally indicated by the IQ score which deviates two standard deviations below average, around 70 or 68; (2) the lack of self-adjustment behavior to the demand of the social environment. The child’s resistance of adaptive behavior is very low, which refers to the low social independency and responsibility compared to others of his/ her age and/ or his/her cultural group; (3) it happens during the developmental periods under the age of 16 or 18.

The retardation of cognitive development in children with intellectual disability becomes a big problem when they are pursuing their developmental tasks. Effendi (2009) explained some barriers in cognitive aspects which appear in children with intellectual disability and at once become their characteristics, i.e.: (1) tend to have a concrete thinking ability and find difficulties to reason, (2) have difficulties to concentrate, (3) their social abilities are very limited, (4) unable to understand difficult instructions, (5) unable to analyze and to judge the events that they faced, and (6) for the children with mild intellectual disability, their highest achievements in reading, writing and counting is not more than the capability of normal children of grade three until grade five in primary school.

DJK and Balakrishnan (2013) explained that the challenges faced in the inclusion of students with special needs are very complex and diverse. Especially for students with intellectual disability in moderate and severe category, to adapt with regular school environment and learning process sometimes creates frustrations which impacts

on their ability to absorb the lessons. Supena (2015) stated that the general curriculum and learning strategies might not be effective for them since their intellectual capacities are inadequate. The learning process needs to be modified, arranged and adjusted based on their conditions, to be able to get an optimal result.

Similar to what Supena has described previously, DJK & Balakrishnan (2012) stated: *"The curricular aim recommended is to provide an education to equip students to live as independent a life as possible by them, in a community which may not always be fully cognizant of their needs"*. Hence, it should be realized by the teachers that the unsuccessfulness of students with intellectual disability to accomplish the tasks given is merely caused by the level of ability which is not in accordance with the tasks' level of difficulties. The learning program should be based on individual developmental model which considers mental age and not chronological age (Delphie, 2009).

Supena (2015) explained that there are some concepts, strategies and principals that need to be considered in creating an optimal learning process for students with intellectual disability, namely: (1) modification of content, process, evaluation. It is a process to change the general learning strategy to be adjusted with the conditions and the needs of students with intellectual disability, so that the learning process can run effectively and efficiently, (2) functionality, which relates to the usefulness of the learning in their daily life, (3) tasks analysis, which relates to the students with intellectual disability's thinking process ability, (4) Individualized Learning Program, which emphasizes on the needs of students with intellectual disability to have an individual learning service, and (5) peer learning, as a strategy or a way of teaching where another student is utilized to help and to guide students with intellectual disability.

In addition to the curriculum for students with intellectual disability, according to Supena (2017), there are four main aspects to be highlighted, which are: modification of the goal, modification of the content, modification of the process, and modification of the evaluation. While four possible main models which can be considered in developing inclusive education curriculum are: duplication (using the same curriculum as the other normal students), modification (the curriculum is modified according to the student's needs and abilities), substitution (the curriculum is changed according to the student's needs and abilities), and omission (the curriculum is eliminated because it does not comply with the student's needs and abilities).

An educational service for students with intellectual disability in regular schools is one form of inclusive education. Supena (2015) defined inclusive education as an ideology, a system or a strategy in organizing education, where every child from any background and conditions are able to join in the same educational environment, with an educational service system being adjusted to the students' conditions. Lipsky & Gartner (in Downing, 2010) stated that *"Inclusive education is full-time membership of students with disabilities in their chronologically age-appropriate classrooms with the necessary supports and services to benefit from educational activities."* While in article 1 of Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009, inclusive education is defined as an educational organization system which provides opportunities to all students who have disabilities

as well as students with potential intelligence and/or special gifts to get education and to follow the learning process in the same educational environment as the other students in general.

The aims of inclusive education in Indonesia are described clearly in article 2 Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009, i.e.: (a) to provide a wide range of opportunity to all students with physical, emotional, mental and social disabilities, as well as students with potential intelligence and/or special gifts to get a good quality of education in accordance to their needs and capabilities; and (b) to actualize the implementation of education which appreciates diversity and indiscriminative for every student as stated in point a.

Related to the aims of inclusive education mentioned previously, Dash (2012) stated that *“The goal of inclusion is to ensure that all children, regardless of any individual differences they may have, are fully included in the mainstream of life.”* It gives benefits not only for the students with special needs, but also for all the parties involved. According to Supena (2015), there are some benefits of the implementation of inclusive education, i.e.: (1) it increases the opportunities for students with special needs to get educational service; (2) it gives a lesson for the society to live side by side with children with special needs; (3) it gives a lesson for children with special needs to be able to live in a general environment; and (4) it lightens the Special Needs School tasks in providing educational services for children with special needs.

The main character in inclusive education implementation cannot be separated from unlimited openness and cross backgrounds to provide a wide opportunity for every student who needs an indiscriminative education service. Therefore, by reading the characteristics of inclusive education, at least there are some important points related to self-adjustment process and flexibility in various aspects to be able to examine urgent necessities for students with special needs. Flexibility is closely related to how inclusive education implementation can give easiness to the students with special needs, and the curriculum given is adjusted to their intellectual level (Ilahi, 2016).

2. Research Methodology

This research is conducted in Victory Plus Primary School, which is located on Kemang Pratama Raya Street, Block AN 2-3, Bojong Rawalumbu, Bekasi – 17116. This school is implementing IB (*International Baccalaureate*) curriculum which is combined with national curriculum. From the overall number of more or less 360 students, there are around 13 students with special needs, with different kinds of disabilities, and three of them are diagnosed as intellectually disabled. It is an evaluation research that uses qualitative method. Qualitative method means that the research’s findings are not obtained through statistics procedures or any other forms of counting. Likewise, this research is giving a descriptive and thorough illustration about the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability in Victory Plus Primary School.

Data collection was carried-out through several techniques such as observations, interviews, and documents analysis. Observations were performed directly in the venue to get a clear description about the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability. Moreover, interviews were conducted against several homeroom teachers who have students with intellectual disability in their class, some shadow teachers, curriculum coordinator, counselor, and also the principal. Some documents gathered to be analyzed are the assessment reports and also the school reports. Some information was also obtained from a key informant as a comparison to the data gathered in the field. After that, data were processed using Miles and Huberman data analysis technique, which involved three activities at the same time, such as: (1) data reduction, which is the process of selection, concentration and transformation of raw data gained from the field; (2) data presentation, which is the process of classifying similar data to several categories in order to make it easier to read and to conclude; and (3) conclusion withdrawal, which is the process of withdrawing the conclusions from the data that have been categorized previously.

In this research, data validation were done by using repeated observations and by doing data sources triangulation, where data gained from specific data sources were compared with data gained from other sources. Confirmations or comparisons were also done with data gathered from the key informant, which is an expert in inclusive education.

2. Results

Based on the research results, it is known that Victory Plus Primary School has been implementing inclusive education for more or less three years since the school has a counselor. Next, the discussion of inclusive education implementation for students with intellectual disability in Victory Plus Primary School will be divided into eight sub-focus. First is about the profile of students with intellectual disability. This school has three students with intellectual disability, which is known from the result of their intelligence test. Two from the three students, namely "S" and "M" have shadow teachers to accompany them in their learning process. While the other one, namely "N" does not have any shadow teacher. According to his homeroom teacher, the reason is because procedurally there has to be an upright diagnose about the students' needs and capabilities. But since his parents are not cooperative enough to assess their child to be able to get an upright diagnose, so the school has not been able to decide whether this student needs a shadow teacher or not.

The following are the profile of three students with intellectual disability who study in inclusive education setting at Victory Plus Primary School. "S" is a male student who studies in grade 1 with IQ score of 66. During infancy, he experienced seizures several times. He also experienced speech delay and started to speak in the age of five years. He has been studying up to grade two in Bahrain, but when he registered in Victory Plus Primary School, based on the observation and assessment result, he could not continue his education in grade three. Instead, he had to study over again in

grade one. It is also known from his assessment result that his non-verbal intelligence is better than his verbal intelligence, and his numerical reasoning is also better than his verbal reasoning. His social-emotional abilities are quite good, and he does not have any trouble in socializing with his friends.

“N” is a male student who studies in grade three with IQ score of 68. Based on the assessment result, it is known that his abilities in concentrating and organizing visual and motor movements, as well as processing verbal information are far below the average of children in his age. His parents are over protective and tend to serve all his needs, and it makes him become less independent. His intellectual ability is very limited. He is often unable to give the appropriate response when given a question, or when in a discussion.

“M” is a male student who studies in grade four with IQ score of 65. Based on the assessment result, it is known that his theoretical verbal abilities and his practical performance abilities are far below the average of children in his age. When he was still in the womb, his mother got a serious illness. During infancy, he also experienced seizures several times. For his social-emotional aspect, he is having difficulties to socialize with his friends. He tends to be alone and rarely interacts with his friends.

The second sub-focus is about teachers’ competencies. As it is mentioned in article 29 of Government Regulation number 19, 2005, that primary school teachers’ academic qualification is Diploma or Bachelor degree in the field of Primary Education, other kinds of education, or Psychology. All the teachers in Victory Plus Primary School hold a Bachelor Degree, although not all of them are from educational background. Some teachers are from Economic background, some of them are from Law, and some of them are from French Literature. Moreover, some teachers have gained their master degree in several majors such as Education Management, Indonesian Literature and Social Studies. However, it is known from the interviews, that the teachers’ knowledge about special needs education is still insufficient for them to be able to handle the students with special needs in their class.

Dr. Wuriyani, M.Pd, a lecturer in Special Needs Education Department, Faculty of Education, Jakarta State University, who acts as a key informant in this research, said that teachers should at least 60% know the needs of their students. It means that the teachers have to be equipped by the ability to recognize who their students are, including their needs, their abilities, and their way of study. The knowledge about students with special needs as mentioned by Dr. Wuriyani above has not been owned by most teachers in Victory Plus Primary School. Aside from their educational backgrounds which are not from educational field, the school itself is not giving sufficient trainings related to this matter.

The third sub-focus is about curriculum for students with intellectual disability. In article 7 of Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009, it is written that a school which implements inclusive education needs to use their own curriculum for the students with intellectual disability that accommodate the students’ needs and abilities in accordance with their talents and interests. From the three students with intellectual disability who study in Victory Plus Primary School, only “M” who already uses a

modified curriculum, while the other two, namely “S” and “N” are still using the general curriculum which is the same one used by the other normal students. It obviously becomes an obstacle in their learning process because academically they are unable to follow the curriculum. For “S” and “N”, the curriculum model that they use mostly is duplication model, which is exactly the same curriculum as what the other normal students use. On the other hand, “M” uses modification model in Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, Indonesian Language and ICT subjects. While in Religion, PE, Music and Visual Arts subjects, he uses duplication model, which is exactly the same with the other normal students. Specifically for English and Mandarin, he uses omission model. In other words, it is omitted with the consideration that the two subjects are less functional for him.

As mentioned by Ilahi (2016), that an important point that becomes the characteristic of inclusive education is the flexible curriculum. Therefore, the curriculum adjustment should be done by stressing out on the fulfillment of the learning needs which is adapted with the students with special needs’ abilities. Similarly, Supena (2015) also explained that the general curriculum and learning strategy might not be effective for the students with intellectual disability, as their intellectual capabilities are inadequate. Hence, for students with intellectual disability, the curriculum used should be properly adjusted with their needs and abilities.

The fourth sub-focus is about facilities that support the learning of students with intellectual disability. In article 46 of Government Regulation number 19, 2005, it is stated that any school which has students, teachers or staffs who needs special services is required to provide access to the facilities in accordance with their needs. Data related to facilities in Victory Plus Primary School were obtained from interviews and observations. Based on observations, the existing facilities are classes equipped with air conditioner, chairs, tables, bookshelves, carpets, whiteboards, and computers. Meanwhile, there are also several infrastructures such as library, playground, soccer field, basketball court, computer lab, swimming pool, food technology, elevator, hall, multipurpose room, mosque, music room, and common room. Various kinds of learning media are also used, whether it is digital or non-digital. From all the facilities and infrastructures provided in Victory Plus Primary School, only a few of them are specifically allocated for students with intellectual disability. Although there is a room that is used for them to learn how to read and write, it is only an empty room without specific media that can help to support their learning.

Actually, according to Dr. Wuriyani, specific facilities for students with intellectual disability are very important to train their balance, focus and to develop their sensory. The provision of facilities that can develop the sensory of students with intellectual disability, as what she mentioned above, can also give good impacts for the students’ development. One of them is that the students with intellectual disability are able to develop their non-academic aspects which can be beneficial for their future life.

The fifth sub-focus is about the learning process of students with intellectual disability in inclusive education setting. The learning process in inclusive education, as it is mentioned in article 8 of Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009, should

consider the learning principles, and should be adjusted with the students' learning characteristics. A flexible learning process can give convenience and easiness for students with intellectual disability to perform the activities which are related to the development of their skills and potentials in order to build their bright future (Ilahi, 2016). Furthermore, Supena (2015) revealed that there are some concepts, strategies or principles that need to take into account in preparing the learning process for students with intellectual disability so it can work optimally. One of which is process modification, that can be considered as the effort to change the way of teaching so it can be easier to follow. There are some steps to be done, such as simplifying explanatory language, extending the learning time, simplifying and elaborating the work steps, giving concrete examples, using concrete and simple media, involving as many sensory experiences as possible, etc.

Based on research findings, it is known that "S" is still doing the same learning process as the other normal students in his class for all subjects. However, there is a shadow teacher who always guides and helps him intensively in order for him to understand the learning materials given. "N" is also having the same learning process and the same learning materials as the other normal students in his class for all subjects. He does not have any shadow teacher, so the homeroom teacher needs to apply some strategies and do lots of guidance for him. While for "M", since he has modified curriculum for Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, Indonesian Language and ICT subjects, so the learning materials are different from his friends. In those subjects, even though he sits in the same class as his friends, but he is not involved in the learning process happening in the class. Instead, he is learning his own learning materials with his shadow teacher in one corner of the class. It is different for Religion, PE, Music and Visual Art subjects, where he follows the same learning process as his normal friends without any modification at all. While for English and Mandarin subjects, he usually pulled out and learns in another room to catch up the learning materials in other subjects. For the subjects which curriculum is modified, the teaching plans are made by his shadow teacher guided by the curriculum coordinator and counselor.

Based on the interviews and observations, it is found that there are several model of learning process done by students with intellectual disability in inclusive education setting at Victory Plus Primary School. They are: (1) Teacher explains the materials in general, after that, shadow teacher re-explains the materials and help the student to do the task given. This model is performed by "S" and "M"; (2) Teacher explains the materials in general, and then when it comes to the assignments, peers help the student to understand the materials and the assignment. This model is performed by "N"; (3) Teacher explains the materials in general, and then the teacher re-explains the materials to the student privately before the student does the task given. This model is performed by "S" and "N"; (4) The learning is done privately with a shadow teacher. Shadow teacher is the one who delivers the learning materials and also gives the assignments, although it is done in the same class with the other normal students. This model is performed by "M"; (5) Student learns in a separate room with a shadow teacher to catch up the materials in specific subject. This model is performed by "S" and "M".

The sixth sub-focus is the evaluation for students with intellectual disability. Based on the theory, like what Supena (2015) had mentioned that evaluation modification relates to the attempts of changing the way of evaluating students with intellectual disability. In a certain limit, simple written academic evaluation might be done, but evaluation which assesses a performance or skill in a real and natural situation is much more important and useful for them. In addition, the matter of evaluation is arranged in article 9 of Education Minister Regulation number 70, 2009. It is written that "The learning evaluation for students in inclusive education refers to the curriculum organized by the school." Meanwhile, the evaluation done by students with intellectual disability in Victory Plus Primary School who use the same curriculum as the other normal students are more or less still the same as those done by the other normal students. The following are the explanations of the evaluation done by each of the students with intellectual disability.

Since "S" is using the same curriculum as the other normal students, the content of the evaluation for him is exactly the same as the others. While for the way of evaluation, at first he is given the same way as others, but if he is unable to accomplish it, the teacher will give a different way for him to accomplish the task. For example, at first the evaluation is given in written form, if he finds it difficult, then the teacher will try to evaluate him orally. The time of evaluation is the same as the other normal students, although he always needs extra time to be able to finish his tasks. He does not use any aids to help him to accomplish the tasks, but he is still very dependent on his shadow teacher's help.

"N" also uses the same curriculum as the other normal students, so the content of evaluation for him is exactly the same as the others too. However, his homeroom teacher sometimes modifies the quantity of the questions in the evaluation. Usually he will be given fewer questions than the other students in order for him to be able to finish the tasks on time. The way of evaluation and the time of evaluation are not different from the other normal students in his class. However, he always needs longer time than his friends to finish his tasks.

For "M", for the subjects which use the same curriculum as the other normal students, the content of the evaluation is exactly the same as the other students. While for some subjects who use modified curriculum, the content of evaluation corresponds to the content of the modified curriculum. The way of the evaluation done is also different. It depends on the curriculum, whether it is the same or modified. If the curriculum is the same, then the way of evaluation is also the same. On the other hand, if the curriculum is modified, the way of evaluations usually done in a form of written test, although once in a while the evaluation is done in a form of performance. The time of evaluation for the subjects which use the same curriculum is the same as the other students, but for the subjects which use modified curriculum, it is done at the end of the lesson, when he is already considered to understand the lesson. Like the other two students with intellectual disability, he also needs longer time to be able to accomplish his tasks.

The seventh sub-focus is the role and involvement of student with intellectual disability's parents. It cannot be denied that a good relation and cooperation is needed between the school and the parents so that the education for students with intellectual disability can work effectively and efficiently. However, it is known from the research that the parents of the three students with intellectual disability who study in Victory Plus Primary School are showing less involvement in supporting their child's education. One of the parents still feels reluctant to do the school's recommendation that hinders the process to accommodate the student's education needs.

Several parents' attitude which considered as uncooperative are: spoiling their child, being ignorant to their child's homework, denying their child's deficiency and doing the child's work for him, not supporting their child's learning at home. The parents of the three students with intellectual disability tend to hand over their child's education to the school and give less contribution to synergize with the school in order to support the development of their child. Nevertheless, the school always puts more efforts to establish a good and positive relationship, such as arranging a meeting every three months to discuss and evaluate the progress achieved by the student and to plan the follow-up actions.

The eighth sub-focus is about the supporting and inhibiting factors in implementing inclusive education for students with intellectual disability. In implementing inclusive education for students with intellectual disability in Victory Plus Primary School, obviously there are the supporting and inhibiting factors. According to some teachers, counselor, curriculum coordinator, and principal, the supporting factors are: the presence of a counselor as the expert who can help in giving the right treatments for the students with intellectual disability, the presence of shadow teachers who guide and help the students with intellectual disability in the learning process, the support from the school in making the curriculum modifications for students with intellectual disability, the standard availability in the admission of students with special needs. On the other hand, the inhibiting factors are: the lack of supports and cooperation from the parents of the students with intellectual disability, the lack of coordination among the authorized parties in planning the teaching plan for students with intellectual disability, the unsteady program, and the unprepared curriculum.

3. Conclusions

Based on the explanations above, there are some conclusions that can be drawn. Start from the profile of students with intellectual disability, based on the intelligence test's result, there are three students in Victory Plus Primary School who can be categorized into mild intellectual disability. Teachers' competencies to teach students with intellectual disability in inclusive education setting in their class are inadequate, because most of the teachers do not have enough knowledge to handle them. Besides that, the school has not provided the teachers with trainings to improve their competencies in handling students with intellectual disability yet.

In terms of curriculum, it is still inconsistent, because from three students with intellectual disability who study there, only one who already uses modified curriculum, while the other two still use the same curriculum as the other normal students. Speaking about the modified curriculum used there, it is still in the form of trial and error. It gives the impression that the school is not prepared with the curriculum for students with intellectual disability. From the aspect of facilities and infrastructure, there have not been any facilities which are aimed specifically to support the learning of students with intellectual disability. There are two shadow teachers to help and guide students with intellectual disability in their learning process. However, from three students with intellectual disability who study there, only two are having the shadow teachers, while the other one is not.

There are not any differences in terms of the learning process for the two students with intellectual disability with the other normal students in their class because they are still using the same curriculum as their friends. There is no modification and adjustment in accordance with their needs and abilities. Likewise, the evaluations have not been adjusted to the students with intellectual disability's capabilities, which cause them to experience difficulties in accomplishing the tasks. The parents of the students with intellectual disability are not cooperative enough and showing a little involvements in their child's education. It makes their education development cannot be optimal. Some factors that support the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability in this school are the presence of a counselor as an expert, the presence of shadow teachers to guide and help the learning process of students with intellectual disability, the support from the school in making the curriculum modification, and the standard availability in the admission of students with special needs. On the other hand, the inhibiting factors are the lack of cooperation from the parents of the students with intellectual disability, the lack of coordination among the authorized parties, the unsteady program, and the unprepared curriculum.

4. Recommendations

Some recommendations that can be used to improve the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual disability in Victory Plus Primary School are: (1) there has to be a clear and structured system and procedure in implementing inclusive education for students with intellectual disability, start from the initial assessment and observation, the screening of the student's needs and abilities, the curriculum planning, the learning process, and the interventions that can be undertaken to help the development of their non-academic aspects; (2) in designing the learning process for students with intellectual disability to be able to work optimally, there has to be a modification in the content, process and evaluation for each of them unexceptionally. The selection of learning materials should be functional, in other words, it will be useful for their future life and addressed to non-academic competencies as well; (3) facilities and infrastructures also play an important role in supporting the learning process of

students with intellectual disability. As explained by Dr. Wuriyani that there has to be facilities which can develop the students with intellectual disability's balance, sensory, and also concentration; (4) Victory Plus Primary School should try to apply some strategies to develop good cooperation and relationship with the parents of students with intellectual disability, so their support and involvements can be optimal in their child's education development.

References

1. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders Fifth Edition*. (2013). Washington DC: American Psychiatric Publishing.
2. Dash, Neena. (2012). *Inclusive Education for Children with Special Needs*. Delhi: Atlantic.
3. Delphie, Bandi. (2012). *Pembelajaran Anak Tunagrahita: Suatu Pengantar Dalam Pendidikan Inklusi*. Bandung: PT Refika Aditama.
4. DJK, Cornelius dan Janaki Balakrishnan. (2012). *Inclusive Education for Students with Intellectual Disability*. Amsterdam: Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development Journal. Volume 23, No. 2.
5. Downing, June E. (2010). *Academic Instruction for Students with Moderate and Severe Intellectual Disabilities in Inclusive Classroom*. California: Corwin.
6. Efendi, Mohammad. (2009). *Pengantar Psikopedagogik Anak Berkelainan*. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
7. Ilahi, Mohammad Takdir. (2016). *Pendidikan Inklusif: Konsep dan Aplikasi*. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media.
8. Kustawan, Dedy. (2012). *Pendidikan Inklusif dan Upaya Implementasinya*. Jakarta: PT Luxima Metro Media.
9. Sunardi dan Sunaryo. 2011. *Manajemen Pendidikan Inklusif*. Jakarta: Jassi_Anakku. Vol. 10, No. 2.
10. Supena, Asep. 2009. *Model Pendidikan Inklusi Bagi Anak Tunagrahita Di Sekolah Dasar*. Jakarta: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar. Vol. 10, No. 1.
11. Supena, Asep. 2017. *Model Pendidikan Inklusif Untuk Siswa Tunagrahita Di Sekolah Dasar*. Jakarta: Jurnal Parameter. Vol. 29, No. 2.
12. Supena, Asep. 2015. *Pengantar Pendidikan Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Jakarta: Lembaga Pengembangan Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).